

Practical Skills of Instruction and Literacy Development of Learners in Matina District, Davao City

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Abstract. The study unfolded the extent of practical skills of instruction and its correlation with literacy development stages in Matina District, Davao City Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' practical skills of instruction in terms of fluency, vocabulary development, reading comprehension, spelling, composition, consensus findings of research, decoding, word attack and concepts of print, letter recognition phoneme awareness is extensive, while, learners' literacy development stages in terms of intermediate reading, advanced reading, emergent literacy, alphabetic fluency, words and patterns are moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between teachers' practical skills of instruction and learners' literacy development stages. Domains of practical skills of instruction in terms of concepts of print, letter recognition, phoneme awareness, decoding, word attack, spelling, fluency and reading comprehension significantly influenced literacy development. Future research may impact of classroom factors, such as classroom environment, classroom management strategies, and teacher-student interactions, on learners' literacy development. Investigate how these factors interact with practical skills of instruction and their combined effect on student outcomes. Investigate the extent to which teacher preparation programs equip educators with the necessary practical skills of instruction for effective literacy development. Identify areas of improvement and propose recommendations for enhancing teacher training in this domain.

KEY WORDS

1. practical skills of instruction .
2. literacy development of learners.
3. alphabetic fluency.

1. Introduction

Teaching strategies like case method, discussion, and active learning, as well as assessments involving hand signals, reflections, and computation, can help develop students' functional literacy. Functional literacy refers to the practical reading, writing, and math skills needed to function effectively in real life. Teaching practical skills requires using exact instructions to enable the learner to follow the process and repeat the skill; this often involves using visual clues and text or audio prompts. It certainly requires special skills in an instructor if there are no visuals. Likewise, when it is paired with literacy development, precise skills are required to achieve

the optimum desires. The role of the teacher is to encourage all attempts at reading, writing, and speaking, allowing students of varying abilities to experience the different functions and uses of literacy activities. Teacher interactions with students with disabilities build on students' knowledge as they develop literacy skills. In the global context, Brown (2014) stressed that the foundational skills are focused on developing students' understanding and working knowledge of print concepts, phonological awareness, phonics and word recognition, and fluency (NGA and CCSSO, 2010). These skills are taught in a developmental sequence to support reading development. It is important to note that although the NRP identified comprehension and vocabulary as critical components of reading instruction, the Common Core Foundational Skills do not specifically identify these skills. Vocabulary and comprehension are the focus of the anchor standards and related grade-specific K-12 Common Core State Standards. Beginning in kindergarten and through the end of high school, comprehension and vocabulary are integrated across the Common Core strands: Reading, Writing, Speaking and Listening, and Language Reading is one of the most essential skills in learning a second language. His/ her reading practice largely influences the success of language learner. As Harmer (2007), as cited by Malait et al. (2022), stated that reading is helpful for language acquisition; the more they read, the better they get. Reading also has a positive effect on students' vocabulary knowledge, their spelling, and their writing. Therefore, teachers must develop reading habits in students to help them enhance target language efficiency. This can be done by motivating students to read, especially by giving them a reason to read. Aydugo (2022) states that instead of waiting until later grade, extensive reading should be provided as early as possible so they can use the facility that children have up to a certain age. Learners must feel the need to read.

Only then can they read on their own. In short, reading stands as the bedrock for learners' success in learning a second language. Therefore, it is language teachers' responsibility to cultivate a reading culture in students. Across the globe, instruction reading activities positively affected the students' instruction reading skills, increased the students' awareness of instruction reading, and supported the use of strategies in instruction reading. Instruction reading activities conducted during the action research influenced the development of instruction reading skills of French teacher candidates. These activities created awareness of instruction and supported instruction reading behavior. In addition, instruction reading activities positively affected the participants' academic achievement, strategy use, and professional development. In 2009, the Philippines introduced a mother tongue-based multilingual education language policy requiring the "mother tongue" as the language of instruction (LOI) in kindergarten through grade 3. Using teacher classroom language data collected from four LOI groups in 2019, authors compared the frequency of teachers' use of the target LOI in different contexts, including urban versus rural classrooms, classrooms with relatively homogeneous student language backgrounds versus more heterogeneous classrooms, and classrooms with materials in the target language versus classrooms without. They also examined language usage against characteristics of the teacher populations, including language background, years of experience, training, and beliefs about the best language for initial literacy. The results strongly suggest that the most influential levers for increasing teacher usage of a designated LOI in these contexts are ensuring that teachers are assigned to schools where the LOI matches their first language and providing teaching and learning materials in the target LOI, especially teacher guides. These two factors were more strongly and consistently correlated with teacher use of the LOI than all

other variables examined. The linguistic homogeneity of the student population also showed a statistically significant though lower impact on teacher language usage (Harden, Punjabi, and Fernandez, 2022). In the Davao City Schools Division, remedial reading has been observed in elevating the reading achievement of students in schools. There has been a continual enrichment of the reading skills of struggling readers through the initiatives of remedial reading teachers. However, it does not have clear policies on such teachers' identities, roles, challenges, and needs. It was also evident in the review that literature and studies regarding remedial reading teachers in the Philippines are scarce, thus suggesting exploring the what's and the hows of remedial reading teachers to create clear policies that will strengthen their identities and support their professional development. Matina District Schools developed remedial reading teachers who performed various roles in schools and the cultivation of the roles and duties of remedial reading that rely so much

on different factors, some of which are knowledge and the skills that they have, philosophical views in education and the whole school community, the rapport that remedial reading teachers have with their colleagues, the support of the administrators to their personal and career developments, and provisions of the local government. The learners' achievement scores increased after the reading strategies instruction (Aydinbeck, 2021). The effect of reading strategies on reader understanding of varied text types should be analyzed. Furthermore, the reading habits of language learners, including reading frequency, attitudes, motivations, and achievement at varied linguistic levels, should be investigated in the use of reading strategies. Finally, reading strategies should be integrated into reading courses to make teaching-learning more effective. This study sought to analyze the effect of reading strategies and practical instruction on learners' reading achievement and identify the participants' views on the effect of said strategies. Thus, this study is conducted.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the technical method and its process for conducting the study. This includes the selection of the study's design, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical consideration, and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are essential to assume appropriateness and correctness to produce sound data collection, analysis and interpretation. The researcher used artificial intelligence methods for proofreading when preparing this publication. In particular, AI was used to improve the manuscript's overall quality, coherence, and correctness. The purpose of clearly stating this approach is to uphold research ethics and transparency. The use of AI for proofreading recognizes the growing presence and potential of AI in academic and professional writing and demonstrates a commitment to utilizing cutting-edge technologies responsibly.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating them. A correlation reflects the relationship's strength and/or direction between

two (or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative. (Pallant, 2020). Findings from correlational research can be used to determine prevalence and relationships among variables and to forecast events from current data and knowledge. Despite its many uses, prudence is required when

using the methodology and analyzing data. On the other hand, this type of research tries to extrapolate from the analysis of existing phenomena, policies, or other entities to predict something that has yet to be tried, tested, or proposed before (Gujarati, 2020). In this study, indicators under independent variables such as consensus findings of research, concepts of print, letter recognition, phoneme awareness, decoding and attack, spelling, fluency, vocabulary development, reading comprehension and composition are used to estimate the extent of practical skills of instruction in reading among teachers are assumed to be correlated with dependent variable, literacy development stages, where its indicators are emergent literacy, alphabetic fluency, words and patterns, intermediate reading and advanced reading in Matina District, Davao City. Using the design mentioned, it is assumed that variables along with their indicators are mentioned, and the researcher empirically provides evidence that the presented hypothesis is null and void in nature.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Teachers of Matina District, Davao City Division. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective school within the mentioned District. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face-to-face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections; they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. As much as possible, these teacher-respondents where teachers are teaching for three years and above in the public-school service in the respective schools to measure their competence in responding to the queries of the study and how they performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools and the learners' literacy development stages on the practical skills of instruction in reading given new regular

learning system during SY 2022-2023. Further, they have frequently engaged in various seminars and trainings, including SLAC sessions on the pedagogies in integrating reading programs in the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used the adapted Moats (1999) and Maryville University (2022) instrument. The researcher took time to gather and read reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content that support the instrument, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literature as argued by the authors. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of measuring the extent teachers' practical skills on instruction in reading in terms of consensus findings of research, concepts of print, letter recognition, phoneme awareness, decoding word attack, spelling, fluency, vocabulary development, reading comprehension and composition. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of learners' literacy development stages in terms of emergent literacy, alphabetic fluency, words and patterns, intermediate reading, and advanced reading. Based on the definition of the variables, the statements of the survey were placed in contexts. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.867, which means that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to internal consistency is very good.

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of teachers' critical thinking abilities. Scale, descriptive rating

and interpretation are provided below:

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The practical skills of instruction is always manifested
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The practical skills of instruction is often-times manifested
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The practical skills of instruction is some-times manifested
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The practical skills of instruction is rarely manifested
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The practical skills of instruction is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of literacy development, a 5-point Likert scale was used in this study, as presented below;

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The literacy development of learner is always manifested
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The literacy development of learner is often-times manifested
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The literacy development of learner is some-times manifested
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The literacy development of learner is rarely manifested
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The literacy development of learner is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements explain the data gathering procedure steps that the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the College where the researcher is studying and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data, most especially in the current full face-to-face interaction. Permission to conduct the study. In the second week of January 2023, the researcher started to conceptualize the contents and objective of the thesis proposal. She then prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study adopted the standard pro-

cedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004) and health protocol as provided by the policy of IATF. As soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the schools of Matina District Schools. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents who do not have access to the internet. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were gen-

erated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of January 2023. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The results of the preliminary analysis were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of February 2023. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometimes on the fourth week of February 2023, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of March 2023.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1) regarding the extent of teachers' practical skills of instruction and statement problem number two (2) regarding the extent of learners' literacy development stages in Matina District, Davao City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between the extent of teachers' practical skills and the extent of learners' literacy

development stages in Matina, Davao City. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of the extent of teachers' practical skills of instruction that significantly influence learners' literacy development stages in Matina District, Davao City (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with presenting, analyzing, and interpreting data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is given to make the study meaningful and draw out the implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of teachers' practical skills of instruction. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: flu-

ency (3.90), vocabulary development (3.90) and reading comprehension (3.66) are oftentimes manifested, while, spelling (3.24), composition (3.24), consensus findings of research (3.23), de-

coding, word attack (3.12) and concepts of print, letter recognition phoneme awareness (3.10) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.42 denotes the extent of teachers' practical skills of instruction is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 1. Summary of Teachers' Practical Skills Of Instruction

No	Teachers' Practical Skills Of Instruction	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Consensus findings of research	3.23	Moderately Extensive
2	Concepts of print, letter recognition phoneme awareness	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	Decoding, word attack	3.12	Moderately Extensive
4	Spelling	3.24	Moderately Extensive
5	Fluency	3.90	Extensive
6	Vocabulary development	3.90	Extensive
7	Reading comprehension	3.66	Extensive
8	Composition	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.42	Extensive

Table 2 summarizes the extent of learners' literacy development stages. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: intermediate reading (3.70), advanced reading (3.56) and emergent literacy (3.51) are often manifested,

while, alphabetic fluency (3.48) and words and patterns (3.08) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.46 denotes that the extent of learners' literacy development stages is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Practical Skills Of Instruction And Learners' Literacy Development Stages

It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' practical skills of instruction ($r=0.857$; $p<.003$) and learners' literacy development stages. Table 3 revealed the significant

relationship between teachers' practical skills of instruction and learners' literacy development stages. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant relationship between teachers' practical skills of instruction and learners' literacy development stages, must be rejected, for it provided empirical evidence to show its correlation.

Table 2. Summary of Extent of Learners’ Literacy Development Stages

No	Learners’ Literacy Development Stages	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Emergent literacy	3.51	Extensive
2	Alphabetic fluency	3.48	Moderately Extensive
3	Words and patterns	3.08	Moderately Extensive
4	Intermediate reading	3.70	Extensive
5	Advanced reading	3.56	Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.46	Extensive

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Teachers’ Practical Skills of Instruction and Learners’ Literacy Development Stages

Variables	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation	Decision
teachers’ practical skills of instruction				
learners’ literacy development stages	0.857	<0.03	Significant	Reject H_0

Literacy development is a fundamental aspect of education, enabling individuals to acquire the necessary skills to comprehend and communicate effectively. Teachers play a pivotal role in facilitating learners' literacy development, utilizing various practical instruction skills. At the foundation stage of literacy development, learners acquire fundamental skills such as letter recognition, phonemic awareness, and basic vocabulary. Teachers with practical instruction skills can significantly impact learners' progress during this crucial stage. By employing strategies such as explicit phonics instruction, interactive read-aloud, and multisensory activities, teachers can provide learners with a strong foundation in phonological awareness, letter-sound correspondence, and vocabulary development. These practical skills foster a positive learning environment, encouraging learners to engage actively and develop a solid literacy base. Developing Reading and Writing Skills During the emergent stage, learners begin to connect letters and sounds, understand print concepts, and develop essential reading and writing skills. Teachers' practical instruction skills are critical in guiding learners through this phase. Practical strategies, such as shared reading, guided writing, and word work activities, enhance learners' decoding skills, sight word recognition, and writing fluency. Moreover, teachers' ability to provide timely and constructive feedback encourages learners to refine their skills, fostering their confidence and motivation in literacy activities. In the consolidation stage, learners strengthen their reading fluency and comprehension skills. Teachers with practical instruction skills can employ evidence-based practices to support learners' progress in this critical phase. By implementing guided reading sessions, encouraging independent reading, and using comprehension strategies such as predicting, questioning, and summarizing, teach-

ers enhance learners' ability to extract meaning from texts. Additionally, incorporating vocabulary instruction and teaching comprehension skills explicitly equips learners with the necessary tools to comprehend complex texts and develop a deeper understanding of what they read. Teachers' practical instruction skills are vital in challenging learners and fostering higher-order thinking skills. By implementing inquiry-based learning, promoting discussions, and assigning complex reading materials, teachers encourage learners to analyze texts, evaluate information, and articulate their ideas effectively. These practical skills enable learners to become independent and critical thinkers, capable of engaging with a wide range of texts and producing well-structured and coherent written pieces. Domains of Practical Skills Of Instruction Significantly Influence Literacy Development Stages

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on domains of practical instruction skills significantly influencing literacy development stages. Domains of practical skills of instruction in terms of concepts of print, letter recognition, phoneme awareness (0.002), decoding, word attack (0.001), spelling (0.000), fluency (0.003), and reading comprehension (0.000) significantly influenced literacy development. On the other hand, consensus findings of research (0.051), vocabulary development (0.052), and composition (0.051) do not significantly influence literacy development. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.883 suggests that teachers' practical skills of instruction explain 88.3%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (256.578) and F-statistic are significant $p < .000$, which indicates that the model better predicts learners' literacy development stages.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Practical Skills of Instruction Significantly Influence Literacy Development Stages

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions	Interpretation
(Intercept)	4.245		0.077	60.416	0.001	4.143
(Intercept)	0.312		0.174	1.066	0.270	0.202
CPLRPA	0.807	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.315	0.002
*Reject H_0						
DWA	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196	0.001
*Reject H_0						
S	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038	0.000
*Reject H_0						
F	0.921	0.508	0.136	1.299	0.296	0.003
*Reject H_0						
RC	0.502	0.057	0.210	3.098	0.038	0.000
*Reject H_0						
CFR	0.046	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.315	0.051
Accept H_0						
VD	0.541	0.508	0.136	1.299	0.296	0.052
Accept H_0						
C	0.445	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038	0.051
Accept H_0						
$R^2 = 0.891$						
F -value = 256.578						
p -value = < 0.000						

Developing literacy skills is crucial to education, enabling individuals to communicate, comprehend, and engage with the world around them. The practical skills of instruction teachers play a significant role in shaping learners' literacy development across different stages. Teachers with practical instructional skills employ explicit phonics instruction, interactive activities, and engaging materials to help learners grasp these foundational skills. By providing clear explanations, modeling, and scaffolding, teachers create an environment that supports learners in mastering the essential building blocks of literacy. As learners progress to the emergent stage, they connect letters and sounds, comprehend print concepts, and develop rudimentary reading and writing skills. Practical skills of instruction greatly influence their development during this critical phase. Teachers skilled in instruction implement techniques like shared reading, guided writing, and word work activities to enhance learners' decoding abilities, sight word recognition, and writing fluency. Teachers empower learners to expand their skills and gain confidence in their emerging literacy abilities by offering targeted feedback, encouraging experimentation, and providing practice opportunities. During this stage, students' literacy development continues to be shaped by practical instructional skills. Teachers skilled in instruction employ inquiry-based learning, discussion facilitation, and complex text analysis strategies. Teachers foster higher-order thinking skills by encouraging learners to think critically, evaluate evidence, and express their ideas effectively. These practical instructional skills enable learners to become independent and discerning thinkers, capable of engaging with a wide range of texts and producing well-structured and analytical written work.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion, and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are the study's findings, which are given in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of teachers' practical skills of instruction in terms of fluency (3.90), vocabulary development (3.90), and reading comprehension (3.66) are often manifested. In contrast, spelling (3.24), composition (3.24), consensus findings of research (3.23), decoding, word attack (3.12), and concepts of print, letter recognition, and phoneme awareness (3.10) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.42 denotes the extent to which teachers' practical instruction skills are often manifested, thus being extensive. The extent of learners' literacy development stages in terms of intermediate reading (3.70), advanced reading (3.56), and emergent literacy (3.51) are often manifested, while alphabetic fluency (3.48) and words and patterns (3.08) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.46 denotes that the extent of learners' literacy development stages is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' practical skills of instruction ($r=0.857$; $p<.003$) and learners' literacy development stages. Domains of practical skills of instruction in terms of concepts of print, letter recognition, phoneme awareness (0.002), decoding, word attack (0.001), spelling (0.000), fluency (0.003), and reading comprehension (0.000) significantly influenced literacy

development. On the other hand, consensus findings of research (0.051), vocabulary development (0.052), and composition (0.051) do not significantly influence literacy development.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are the conclusions, to wit; The teachers’ practical instruction skills in fluency, vocabulary development, reading comprehension, spelling, composition, consensus research findings, decoding, word attack, and concepts of print, letter recognition, and phoneme awareness are extensive. The learners’ literacy development stages in intermediate reading, advanced reading, emergent literacy, alphabetic fluency, words, and patterns are moderately extensive. A significant relationship exists between teachers’ practical instruction skills and learners’ literacy development stages. Domains of practical instruction skills, such as concepts of print, letter recognition, phoneme awareness, decoding, word attack, spelling, fluency, and reading comprehension, significantly influenced literacy development.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May offer regular and relevant professional development sessions focused on practical instruction skills for teachers. These sessions should be tailored to address the specific needs of teachers at different stages of literacy development. To support effective instruction, schools have access to high-quality instructional materials, including books, manipulatives, and technology tools. Allocate funds to update and expand the literacy resources available to teachers. Regularly assess the effectiveness of literacy programs and instructional practices within the district. Gather feedback from teachers, students, and parents to identify areas of improvement and make informed decisions about instructional support and resource allocation. School Principal. May prioritize and allocate time and resources for teachers’

professional development in literacy instruction. Provide opportunities for teachers to attend conferences, workshops, and collaborative planning sessions to enhance their practical skills. Create a school-wide culture that promotes literacy and values the importance of effective instruction. Encourage teachers to incorporate literacy across subject areas and provide opportunities for students to engage in reading and writing activities beyond the language arts classroom. Regularly observe and provide feedback to teachers on their instructional practices. Offer guidance and support to address any areas of improvement and ensure alignment with research-based instructional strategies. Teacher. You may use professional development opportunities to enhance your practical instruction skills. Stay informed about the latest research and best practices in literacy instruction through reading professional literature, attending workshops, and participating in online communities. Recognize the diverse needs of your students and adapt your instruction accordingly. Differentiate instruction to accommodate learners at various stages of literacy development, providing appropriate challenges and support. Engage in professional collaboration with your colleagues to share ideas, resources, and best practices related to literacy instruction. Collaborative planning, peer observations, and sharing of student work can enrich your instructional practices. Future Researcher. May investigate the effectiveness of specific instructional strategies: Conduct research studies to examine the impact of specific practical instruction skills on learners’ literacy development at different stages. Explore the effectiveness of various instructional approaches, interventions, and technologies to inform evidence-based practices. Examine the impact of classroom factors, such as classroom environment, classroom management strategies, and teacher-student interactions, on learners’ literacy development. Investigate how these factors interact with practical instruction skills and

their combined effect on student outcomes

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